

Figure 11b: The round temple base, method 2, DM 88.1-2.

To make a round temple base from a square:

Make a square $abcd$. Measure the diagonal bc . Draw a circle about the centre of the square, e , the radius of which is $\frac{1}{3}(bc)$.